

D3.7 REPORT ON DEVELOPED COST-EFFECTIVE PROCESS CHAINS

WORK PACKAGE 3

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
B2B	Business to Business
DSC	Differential scanning calorimetry
ICP-OES	Optical emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma
IRR	Internal rate of return (IRR).
MFR	Melt flow rate
NPV	Net Present Value
OIT	Oxidation induction time
PE	Polyethylene
PCR	Post-consumer recyclate
S/L	Solid/liquid
TBS	Tracer-Based-Sorting
WP	Work package

PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Since the start of the project, various sorting, pretreatment, and recycling processes have been evaluated to meet the quality requirements for post-consumer polyethylene recyclate (PE PCR) intended for food packaging applications. The primary objective was to produce high-quality recyclates while minimizing the cost gap between recycled and virgin materials.

To achieve this, UGENT and Fraunhofer analyzed the outcomes of Tasks 3.2 to 3.5 within Work Package (WP) 3. Using the database (see public Deliverable D3.1¹), they identified process chains capable of meeting the desired quality standards. These processes include water washing and water-based deinking as pretreatment steps, as well as dissolution-based recycling for purification and material recovery. Mass and energy balances were calculated for each process chain, covering material yields, water and solvent consumption, and energy requirements for solvent recovery. In parallel, basic cost estimates were developed to support sustainability assessments conducted in WP7.

This deliverable outlines the design of optimized process chains aimed at achieving the highest purification levels at minimal costs for specific input waste streams. These streams include:

- French household flexible post-consumer packaging waste
- Business-to-business (B2B) collected flexible food packaging waste
- Flexible food packaging waste sorted via tracer-based sorting (TBS) for closed-loop recycling

Two recycling cascades have been designed: **Recycling Cascade 1** and **Recycling Cascade 2**.

- **Recycling Cascade 1** involves dissolution-based recycling for purification, including recompounding and finally deodorization as post-treatment.
- **Recycling Cascade 2** involves water-based delamination/deinking and mechanical recycling, followed by deodorization as post-treatment.

The critical factor in selecting the most suitable recycling cascade was the composition and characteristics of the input waste. Findings from WP3 revealed that Recycling Cascade 2 is not suitable for French household post-consumer flexible packaging waste. This is due to the heterogeneous nature of the materials, which are not designed for delamination, significantly reducing the efficiency of water-based processes. The mixed material composition hinders effective ink removal and separation, indicating the need for alternative or enhanced recycling strategies to handle such complex waste streams. Conversely, dissolution-based recycling (Recycling Cascade 1) enabled highly effective purification for this type of waste, allowing the production of machine-direction-oriented (MDOPE) and sealing films with PE PCR content of 50% and 100%, respectively.

For B2B and TBS flexible food packaging waste — which primarily consists of PE-based mono-material flexible packaging laminates designed with a debondable/delamination primer — water-based delamination and deinking (Recycling Cascade 2) proved highly effective. One key

¹ Deliverable D3.1: “Database of studied waste fractions, their analytical results and process cascades they were subjected to” (Public), by Fraunhofer.

advantage of this approach is the existing infrastructure in Europe capable of scaling up these processes, including project subcontractors such as Hydrodyn and NTCP, making this cascade well-suited for these specific waste streams. Deinking efficiencies above 95% were achieved after the integration of specially developed scavengers, which successfully eliminated color staining in PE PCRs — one of the project's key highlights. This cascade is considered the best option for targeted streams such as diverted or B2B streams with dedicated collection systems.

Another major advancement in the project was the integration of deodorization technology into both recycling cascades. A deeper understanding of plastic deodorization, combined with the application of infrared-based technology, enabled deodorization efficiencies exceeding 98% across various waste types, ensuring a safe processing environment for film production.

PE PCR costs — excluding the sorting step — were found to be comparable to current virgin PE market prices (0.80–1.85 €/kg). In both recycling cascades, purification represents the highest cost share in terms of capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX). For water-based purification, the recycled PE needs to be priced above 1.25 €/kg to be commercially viable. While dissolution-based recycling is more expensive due to the additional recompounding step following dissolution, it results in a higher overall CAPEX. The estimated recycled PE cost is 1.40 €/kg for Recycling Cascade 1 and 1.25 €/kg for Recycling Cascade 2. Process feasibility could be further enhanced by improving purification and pretreatment efficiency and integrating renewable energy sources.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Task 3.6, building on the sorting work conducted in WP2, various pretreatment and recycling processes have been developed and implemented in WP3 since the beginning of the project. The main objective was to meet the requirements for food packaging by applying a sequence of pretreatment, recycling, and post-treatment steps to selected input waste materials after sorting.

To achieve this, UGENT and Fraunhofer derived process chains capable of delivering the desired quality. These chains may include Tracer-Based Sorting (TBS), water washing, water-based deinking as pretreatment steps, followed by mechanical or dissolution-based recycling, and deodorization as a post-treatment step. Within the project, these defined sequences of processes are referred to as *recycling cascades*.

The process sequence for each recycling cascade was determined based on the type of input waste material and the results obtained in Tasks 3.2 to 3.5. Mass and energy balances were calculated for each process chain, including yields, water consumption, net solvent usage, and energy demand for solvent recovery. These were complemented by basic cost estimates to support further sustainability assessments. It should be noted that the cost estimates serve only as rough indicators and are intended primarily for comparative purposes.

Based on the types of flexible packaging waste considered in the project, two recycling cascades were developed. These cascades were designed through an evaluation of purification requirements and basic cost assessments.

- **Chapter 2** of this deliverable describes the design of the recycling cascades.
- **Chapter 3** reports on the properties of the post-consumer recycle (PCR) resins that were characterized. These PCRs were produced using the specified recycling cascades and the corresponding input waste streams.
- **Chapter 4** presents the basic cost assessments, focusing solely on the pretreatment, recycling, and post-treatment steps of the recycling cascades. The sorting step was not included in this cost analysis, as the emphasis here is on evaluating the cost structure of the recycling cascades themselves.
- **Chapter 5** provides the final conclusions.

2. RECYCLING CASCADES DESIGNED

2.1. Input flexible packaging waste types

One of the key factors influencing the design of the recycling cascades is the type of input flexible packaging waste. Three different types of input packaging waste have been considered in the project:

1. Tracer-Based Sorted (TBS) PE-based mono-material flexible food packaging pouches (referred to as *LOOP 3* input waste material)
2. Business-to-Business (B2B) PE-based mono-material flexible food packaging, mimicking commercial and industrial waste collected from companies (referred to as *LOOP 2* input waste material)
3. French household flexible packaging waste (referred to as *LOOP 1* input waste material)

Schematic overviews of the processing steps for these three loops—encompassing sorting, purification, recycling, and the subsequent production of novel flexible packaging materials—are shown in Figure 1 (*LOOP 3*), Figure 2 (*LOOP 2*), and Figure 3 (*LOOP 1*). The processing steps addressed in this deliverable are highlighted with yellow frames in each figure.

The recycling cascades have been designed according to the specific characteristics of the input waste types. For instance, in the case of PE-based mono-material flexible packaging, a water-based delamination and deinking route was selected, consisting of water washing, water-based deinking, and mechanical recycling.

For the recycling of multilayered French household flexible packaging waste (Figure 4), a different route was required—namely, washing followed by dissolution-based recycling. This approach was selected due to the complex, mixed nature of the collected household waste, which includes multi-material, multilayer laminates not originally designed within the project scope. Such laminates are unsuitable for recycling via water-based deinking and mechanical processes.

Each recycling cascade has been carefully selected to match the complexity of the flexible packaging waste composition and the recyclate quality that can realistically be achieved using currently available commercial recycling equipment.

Figure 1: Schematic view of LOOP 3 (yellow sketched rectangle represents the processes discussed in this deliverable). LOOP 3 consisted of 2 cycles.

Figure 2: Schematic view of LOOP 2 (yellow sketched rectangle represents the processes discussed in this deliverable)

Figure 3: Schematic view of LOOP 1 (yellow sketched rectangle represents the processes discussed in this deliverable)

Figure 4: French flexible packaging waste fraction used as input waste in LOOP 1

Two distinct recycling cascades have been identified within WP3, each tailored to different input waste streams. A recycling cascade refers to a specific sequence of processing steps applied to waste materials:

- **Recycling Cascade 1** involves dissolution-based recycling, which is preceded by washing or short deinking and followed by deodorization.
- **Recycling Cascade 2** utilizes water-based purification methods, including delamination and deinking, followed by mechanical recycling processes such as densification, melting, and pelletizing, and concluding with deodorization.

Section 2.2 provides a detailed description of Recycling Cascade 1, while Section 2.3 outlines Recycling Cascade 2. The specific types of input materials for each cascade are described within their respective sections.

2.2. Recycling Cascade 1

A schematic overview of Recycling Cascade 1 is presented in Figure 5. This cascade represents the only viable option for recycling polyethylene (PE)-rich, household multi-material flexible packaging. Consequently, the large-scale recycling of the LOOP 1 material (WP6, Task 6.2) was carried out using this cascade, following the process steps illustrated in the figure.

Figure 5: The schematic view of the Recycling Cascade 1

Detailed information on the dissolution-based purification and recycling developments undertaken in Task 3.4 is provided in Deliverable D3.9: “Application of CreaSolv® Recycling Process on Post-Consumer Flexible Plastic Packaging Waste at Demo-Scale Plant (Nominal Capacity: 25 kg/h) by Fraunhofer.” A key step in this cascade is the successful integration of the dissolution-based purification technology with the deodorization process developed by project partner Kreyen.

Recycling Cascade 1 is also suitable for the recycling of newly designed mono-material PE-based flexible coffee packaging laminates, specifically:

1. Those produced for the Business-to-Business collection scenario, and
2. Those marked with tracers.

Small-scale technical recycling trials (3–5 kg) using dissolution-based methods were conducted on these new mono-material PE laminates. These trials demonstrated that the dissolution-based recycling cascade is the preferred route, particularly for complex or mixed waste streams.

However, it is also applicable to other waste streams where high-purity recyclates are required, making it the most broadly applicable cascade identified.

2.3. Recycling Cascade 2

A schematic overview of Recycling Cascade 2 is presented in Figure 6. This recycling cascade is suitable for the recycling of newly designed mono-material PE-based flexible coffee packaging pouches:

1. Used in the Business-to-Business collection scenario, as implemented in WP6 LOOP 2 (Task 6.3),
2. Marked with tracers and sorted, as carried out in WP6 LOOP 3 (Task 6.4).

Figure 6: The schematic view of the Recycling Cascade 2

Following standard pre-treatment steps—such as shredding, washing, grinding, and float-sink separation—the material undergoes water-based purification for delamination and deinking. These procedures, developed in WP3 (Task 3.3), represent a key step in Recycling Cascade 2.

After purification, the resulting flakes are subjected to mechanical recycling steps, including densification, melting, and pelletizing. This is followed by a deodorization post-treatment to remove odors and volatile compounds.

Both recycling cascades require a purification step, either through water-based delamination/deinking or solvent-based dissolution. In both cascades, deodorization is applied as a post-treatment step.

These processes are available at the facilities of the project partners, and in the case of water-based delamination/deinking, at the subcontractor's facilities. The recycling setup is capable of processing 15–20 kg/h of PE material.

A detailed description of the processes used in each recycling cascade is provided in the next section.

2.4. Overview of Individual Processing Steps in the Recycling Cascades

This section describes each of the processes developed and applied within the two designed recycling cascades. These processes include water-based delamination and deinking, mechanical recycling, dissolution-based recycling, and deodorization. Each process step is tailored according to the specific type of flexible post-consumer packaging used as input

- **Water-based Delamination and Deinking as Pre-treatment (UGent):**

For water-based deinking of Recycling Cascade 2, an industrial-scale washing line is used, which can be precisely adjusted through its various components—including hot-wash stages with caustic agents and detergents. The modular system enables each step of the washing process to be individually examined and optimized, allowing variations in solid-liquid ratios, residence time, detergent concentration, and temperature. Additionally, a mechanical dryer and a thermal dryer specifically designed for plastic film are available. The industrial line has a processing capacity of 20 kg/h. The protocols and designs are complete, while construction of the pilot plant at UGent is still ongoing.

Prior to the deinking process, pre-washing is applied to remove physical impurities such as coffee grounds. This step is especially critical for post-consumer plastic waste, where contaminants like dust, grease, and food residues from the use phase can compromise downstream processes. Pre-washing helps prevent saturation of the deinking medium and enhances its performance. Within the project, it was observed that inefficient removal of coffee grounds before deinking reduced deinking efficiency and negatively impacted the quality of the recovered material. Additionally, extracts from the coffee grounds were found to adsorb onto the film surfaces, leading to fuming during later stages of recycling and production. These findings underscore the importance of dry cleaning and pre-washing steps to minimize contamination before deinking and delamination.

Similarly, post-washing the material after deinking is essential to remove residual colorants and reagents from the material's surface.

Deinking can serve as a pre-treatment step in both Recycling Cascade 1 and Recycling Cascade 2. Optimization of the process conditions was conducted at lab scale before scaling up. To effectively remove printing inks from plastic packaging, factors such as particle size, temperature, solid/liquid (S/L) ratio, reagent concentration, and contact time must be carefully controlled. For example, while increasing temperature and particle size can enhance deinking and delamination, it also causes curling in flexible plastic packaging, reducing the material's effective contact with the liquid medium. This phenomenon was observed during deinking trials with materials from Recycling Cascade 2, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Recycling Cascade 2: Deinking (B2B input waste: LOOP 2)

Further insights into the curling behavior of the material were gained through lab-scale optimization studies. It was observed that **temperature** and **flake size** are two critical parameters influencing the degree of curling. While increasing temperature and flake size tends to accelerate deinking and delamination, it also leads to curling in flexible plastic packaging, which reduces effective contact with the liquid medium. A reduction in flake size resulted in significantly less curling, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Deinking: Lab-scale optimization to decrease curling by testing different flake sizes.

The effect of temperature and flake size was also tested in a 5L reactor to observe changes in deinking efficiency and the curling behavior of the material. The output material was then compared to a reference material that had undergone the deinking process but exhibited low deinking efficiency due to curling, as shown in Figure 9. Within the project, this challenge was addressed by optimizing the temperature to balance an accelerated process while minimizing curling.

Figure 9: Recycling Cascade 2: Small pilot scale deinking at optimized temperature and flake size to reduce curling of the material as observed during LOOP 2 material recycling

Reagent concentration also plays a significant role in achieving high deinking efficiency, particularly in large-scale operations. For example, one of the large-scale deinking trials involving the input material used in LOOP 3 (see schematic flow in Figure 10), recycled via Recycling Cascade 2, was carried out under the following operating conditions: 80 °C, with a 1.5% NaOH concentration and a flakes-to-water ratio of 4.2%.

Due to limitations at the subcontractor facility of the project partner NTCP, it was not possible to use higher NaOH concentrations during this process, which led to lower deinking efficiency. However, when the same material was treated in a 5L reactor at UGent using 5% NaOH instead of 1.5%, the deinking efficiency increased from 95% to 99%. The resulting samples are shown in the figure below.

Figure 10: Recycling Cascade 2: Deinking tests of the material at different NaOH concentrations: 1.5% NaOH performed at subcontractor (NTCP) and 5% NaOH which was performed in 5L reactor at UGent.

The solid-to-liquid (S/L) ratio is also a critical parameter. While a high S/L ratio can lead to medium oversaturation and reduced deinking efficiency, it simultaneously increases friction between materials, which aids in delamination. Therefore, optimizing the S/L ratio was essential to balance these opposing effects and enhance the overall process performance.

Additionally, the contact time with the liquid medium must be tailored to the specific input material. For instance, triplex multilayer flexible packaging—developed in WP5 to integrate PE PCR at high concentrations (up to 50%) for flexible food packaging applications—requires a longer contact time compared to duplex structures used for non-food packaging containing PE PCR. Ensuring adequate duration allows for efficient delamination and deinking, thereby improving the quality of the recovered material.

A significant focus of the project was addressing the issue of staining and bleeding. During the deinking process, colorants can undergo reversible adsorption and desorption, leading to persistent staining on the plastic surface. Water-based solutions are limited in their ability to deeply clean the polymers, as they do not sufficiently promote the diffusion of ink and other components from the core of the plastic into the medium. This results in residual contamination, affecting the overall quality of the recycled material. Since water-based deinking had to be used for large-scale processes, the effect of process parameters was thoroughly investigated to

reduce the occurrence of color staining on the deinked material. The list of lab-scale optimizations is presented in Figure 11.

Loop2 conditions at Hydrodyn	Effect of S/L ratio	Effect of contact time	Effect of a second wash with fresh medium	Effect of temperature	Effect of a different detergent
2% S/L ratio 5% NaOH 0,5% detergent 75°C, 120 min	1% and 4% S/L ratios were tested	4h contact	Second time fresh caustic medium	70°C was tested due to curling at 75°C	CTAB was used
Not full deinking Duration is not sufficient High color bleeding	Not full deinking Difficult to mimic large scale trials (different volume, friction)	Deinking and delamination completed High color bleeding	Color bleeding is not improved	Curling still occurs Color bleeding is not improved	Color bleeding is not improved

Figure 11: Lab-scale deinking process optimization on the LOOP 3 Cycle 2 material (L3C2). (Note: Hydrodyn is the subcontractor of UGENT for the deinking process at scale for L3C2)

Initially, the optimized conditions used for LOOP 2 material were tested on LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2) material. However, due to the triplex structure of L3C2, these conditions resulted in low deinking efficiency. The effect of plastic load was assessed by comparing 1% and 4% S/L ratios, but complete deinking could not be achieved. Given the differences in friction mechanisms and tank volume between lab-scale and large-scale processes, replicating large-scale conditions in the lab proved challenging.

The effect of contact time between the plastic and the water-based medium was also evaluated by extending the process duration to 4 hours. This increased interaction time led to complete delamination and effective deinking. However, color staining on the material remained visibly prominent after processing.

To mitigate staining, several strategies were tested: a second wash with fresh water-based medium, lowering the process temperature, and using alternative detergents. Re-contacting the deinked plastic with fresh water-based medium showed no improvement, and neither the reduced temperature nor the addition of a cationic surfactant had a significant effect on minimizing color staining.

As an alternative, a solvent-based medium developed at UGent was tested on the green L3C2 material. After only 30 minutes of contact time, successful delamination and deinking were achieved, and no color bleeding was observed when the solvent-based medium was used.

It was observed that color staining is closely linked to effective medium management. To address this, scavengers developed at UGent were tested at varying concentrations during the water-based deinking of the green L3C2 material. The results showed that the addition of scavengers significantly reduced color staining compared to deinking processes without their use.

Based on these lab-scale process optimization tests at UGent, it was decided to incorporate a scavenger in the upscaling trials at Hydrodyn (a subcontractor of UGent) for the deinking of green L3C2 material. In the first trial, 20 kg of material was shredded into 2 cm flakes, and the deinking process was carried out at 75 °C for 2 hours. The operating conditions included a 1% solid consistency, 5% NaOH concentration, 0.5% detergent concentration, and a solubilized scavenger. However, the residence time was insufficient to achieve effective delamination.

In a second trial, another 20 kg batch was processed under the same conditions, but the interaction time with the liquid medium was extended to 4 hours. As the results were promising, these optimized conditions were applied to a 120 kg deinking trial of L3C2 material conducted at Hydrodyn in September 2024.

The resulting cast film produced after the optimized deinking process—including the use of scavengers—is shown in Figure 12 (far right). The copper content of the three materials displayed in Figure 12 was measured using ICP-OES², with each sample tested in triplicate. The L3C1 recyclate, which was incorporated at 50% into L3C2, already exhibited a blue tint, indicating the presence of copper. It was assumed that the copper content originating from the L3C1 recyclate could not be removed during the deinking of L3C2, as the copper was not present in the ink but was introduced during Cycle 1 recycling and already mixed into the pellets. Therefore, to account for the copper originating from L3C1 recyclate, its copper concentration ($C_{L3C1,Cu\ 50\%}$) was subtracted from both the original (input waste) L3C2 material ($C_{L3C2,Cu}$) and the cast film ($C_{flakes\ deinked,Cu}$) produced after deinking. Afterwards, the percentage of copper removal, *Cu reduction*, was then calculated by dividing the difference in copper concentration between the L3C2 material and the cast film by the copper concentration in L3C2. This calculation is given in the equation below:

$$Cu\ reduction\ \% = \frac{(C_{L3C2,Cu} - C_{L3C1,Cu\ 50\%}) - (C_{flakes\ deinked,Cu} - C_{L3C1,Cu\ 50\%})}{(C_{L3C2,Cu} - C_{L3C1,Cu\ 50\%})}$$

This calculation resulted in a copper reduction of over 95%. However, due to the high standard deviation in copper concentration within the L3C2 material, the reduction percentage was conservatively reported as **greater than 95%**. It is important to note that the cast film used for this calculation was produced at Fraunhofer on a small scale. At the time, the recyclate film from Amcor was not available, so flakes were used for the measurements instead.

Furthermore, since a destructive method was applied prior to the ICP-OES measurements, differences in material form—such as flakes versus pellets—could affect the efficiency and thus contribute to variations in the measured copper content. These factors should be taken into account when interpreting the results.

Figure 12: Left: Colored input material (green, yellow, white, cyan) from LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2) used for large-scale deinking with scavengers developed by UGent. Middle: L3C1 recyclate, incorporated at a 50% ratio into L3C2 production. Right: Cast film produced with 100% PE PCR after the deinking process of L3C2 material.

² ICP-OES: Optical emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma

- **Mechanical recycling (UM and SUEZ): Densification / Melt filtration / Pelletizing:**

In Recycling Cascade 2, the densification step is essential for converting PE film flakes—originating from washing and deinking—into densified pellets that can be further processed through extrusion for melt filtration and subsequent granulation. The equipment available at SUEZ can process up to 50 kg/h via densification, while mechanical recycling at UM includes melt filtration. A processing target of 15–20 kg/h is considered achievable.

Following densification and granulation, a material loss of approximately 2–8% was typically observed. This loss was mainly due to purging of the process line and material residues remaining in the equipment. The resulting granulates were then sent to Kreyenborg for deodorization and subsequently used by Amcor for film production.

If the moisture content of the material received after deinking exceeded 1%, a drying step was implemented prior to densification and granulation.

Regarding the processing of the B2B flexible packaging material from LOOP 2 (Figure 13), a separation step was added prior to densification to remove ground coffee residues that remained in the flakes after washing. Additionally, the presence of two colors (white and yellow) on the flakes led to contamination of the knives in the densifier.

During the processing of LOOP 3 (L3C1) input material, further challenges arose. Ink residues remaining on the surface of the deinked flakes caused contamination of both the densifier and the extruder knives. Furthermore, due to the reagents used in the delamination–deinking process, odor emissions were observed during extrusion and granulation. The resulting granulates exhibited a fishy-like odor.

Figure 13: Left: LOOP 2 (B2B), and Right: LOOP 3 Cycle 2 recyclates after mechanical recycling at SUEZ facilities.

- **Deodorisation (KREYEN) for Post-treatment:**

At the technical laboratory of KREYEN, two main systems are available for deodorization: an Infrared (IR) Batch unit (first treatment step) with a capacity of 60 L, and an IR FRESH CONDITIONER (second treatment step) with a volume of 700 L. Depending on the material form and required treatment duration, throughputs of 15–20 kg/h can be achieved using this setup. If needed, KREYEN can treat volumes of up to 2,000 m³ per day by integrating additional equipment. Figure 14 shows the deodorization facility used at KREYEN.

The following processing conditions were applied during deodorization of materials recycled via both **Recycling Cascade 1** and **Recycling Cascade 2**:

First, the material was treated in the IR-Batch 60-60 drum for 20 minutes at 90 °C. This was followed by a thermal treatment in the air dryer RDX12, operating for 8 hours, during which the material was flushed with air at a flow rate of 7 m³/h and a temperature of 90 °C. In some cases, such as the deodorization of LOOP 3 Cycle 1 material, the air flow was adjusted to 450 m³/h.

This deodorization technique is based on a highly efficient two-phase energy transfer system. In the first phase, the material is processed in an Infrared Dryer (IRD), where it is rapidly heated to near-melting temperatures. The infrared technology heats the material from the inside out, generating a partial pressure gradient that drives odorous compounds from the core to the surface.

In the second phase, the material is transferred to a silo and continuously flushed with hot gas. The elevated temperatures and constant agitation in the IRD promote the rapid diffusion of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from the material into the surrounding atmosphere. The rotating drum ensures continuous movement and surface exposure, bringing each particle close to its melting point and accelerating odor removal.

The combination of fundamental insights into plastic deodorization and the application of infrared-based technology enabled the project to achieve over 98% deodorization efficiency across various types of plastic waste inputs.

Figure 14: IR-based deodorization process applied at Kreyenborg (LOOP 3 Cycle1 PE PCR deodorisation).

- **Dissolution-based Recycling (pilot line) (Fraunhofer IVV):**

Dissolution-based recycling was implemented at various scales within the project: at small technical scale (~5 kg/day), pilot scale (15 kg/h), and industrial demonstration scale with a nominal capacity of 25 kg/h.

This recycling method enables the recovery of high-purity PE recyclate even from mixed waste streams that typically contain a high proportion of composite materials such as multilayer packaging. This means that waste fractions which currently cannot be recycled to high quality, and are therefore typically incinerated, can instead be processed into high-quality recyclate suitable for reuse in the same applications.

This was successfully demonstrated with Recycling Cascade 1, using post-consumer packaging waste fractions from France, Belgium, and Germany, with PE contents ranging from 60–90%. The remaining fraction consisted of incompatible foreign polymers and other materials. Pure PE was selectively extracted and recovered at high quality, free from foreign polymers, making it suitable for film reprocessing and packaging reuse, as demonstrated in LOOP 1 (see Deliverable D6.2³).

Selective solvents play a key role by enabling the targeted dissolution of specific polymers while leaving incompatible materials undissolved. Additional purification steps were shown to effectively remove impurities, further enhancing the recyclate quality. Figure 15 illustrates the difference in film quality between mechanical and dissolution-based recyclates derived from LOOP 1 post-consumer waste.

Figure 15: 70 µm extruded cast films from LOOP 1 material after mechanical recycling (after cold washing and post-sorting by density separation) (left) and dissolution-based recycling (right)

As part of the Recycling Cascade 1 design, various purification steps were tested and shown to improve both the color and odor of the recyclate. These purification procedures were successfully scaled to small technical scale and partially to the industrial demonstration scale. High cleaning efficiency was evidenced not only through visual improvement but also via

³ Deliverable D6.2: “Demonstration of circular use in HPC packaging” (Confidential), by SUEZ.

challenge tests (see public Deliverable D4.4⁴). For LOOP 1 recycling, purification units demonstrated at lab and small-technical scale were validated through challenge tests and deemed suitable for implementation at the demonstration scale. These units played a key role in achieving the highest possible recyclate quality.

In terms of mechanical performance, the high-quality recyclates from LOOP 1 enabled Amcor to produce MDOPE films with 50% PE PCR and sealant films with 67% PE PCR content. These films were laminated to form wet-wipe pouches in a flow-wrap format, resulting in an overall PE PCR content of 62%. Since the packaging is non-contact-sensitive, it was possible to include PCR in both the sealing layer and the MDOPE substrate.

Moreover, it was shown that colorant reduction is not only achievable through additional purification steps (demonstrated at small-technical scale), but also through input stream optimization. Specifically, the dark color of post-consumer recyclates is often caused by a high proportion of dark masterbatch films, and this can be significantly improved by excluding such films during sorting—as shown in Figure 16. This was a key learning during the design of the Recycling Cascade 1, underlining the importance of input material quality for effective recycling.

Figure 16: Recyclate after state-of-the-art dissolution-based recycling (left), excluding black films (middle) and with additional purification (right)

The high cleaning efficiency of the dissolution-based recycling process not only supports the recycling of mixed post-consumer waste fractions (e.g., LOOP 1), but also enables the high-quality recycling of newly designed laminate structures from LOOP 2 and LOOP 3, as discussed in Section 3. Adhesives and printing inks can largely be removed during the dissolution process, resulting in a transparent, nearly colorless recyclate, free from specks and gels, and ready for reuse in high-quality film applications.

⁴ Deliverable D4.4: “Challenge test for demonstration of cleaning efficiency” (Public), by Fraunhofer.

3. PROPERTIES OF POST-CONSUMER RECYCLATES FROM THE TWO RECYCLING CASCADES

3.1. Overview of results

Several small-scale and technical-scale trials were conducted within the project to optimize process parameters and deliver recyclates of the desired quality. Based on the trial results, recycling cascades were designed to process input waste according to its type. The project utilized three different types of input waste, as described in Section 2.1:

1. **LOOP 1:** Flexible packaging household waste.
2. **LOOP 2:** PE-based mono-material B2B flexible packaging.
3. **LOOP 3:** PE-based mono-material laminates with tracers.

For these input streams, intended for the demonstrator loops in WP6, optimized process chains—referred to as recycling cascades—were developed. These designs were based on post-consumer recycling (PCR) assessments of thermal, mechanical, and optical properties, purification levels, and cost structures.

An important criterion in selecting the appropriate recycling cascade was the type of input flexible packaging waste. Findings from WP3 revealed that Recycling Cascade 2 could not be used for the recycling of French household flexible post-consumer waste. This issue arises from the use of mixed packaging materials that cannot be separated during mechanical recycling, preventing the recyclates from being processable into new films. Specifically, the mixed packaging materials are usually not designed to be recyclable, such as they lack a delamination primer, which prevents separation in aqueous media, and further hinders the recyclate's processability in new film production. As a result, **LOOP 1** material was recycled using **Recycling Cascade 1**. Conversely, the more controlled mono-material structures of **LOOP 2** and **LOOP 3**—which are closed-loop systems due to the B2B scenario and TBS (Tracers-Based Sorting), respectively—were successfully recycled at scale using **Recycling Cascade 2**.

Table 1 provides an overview of the production of post-consumer recyclates (PCRs) through the two recycling cascades deployed at scale within the project, focusing on the demonstrator loops in WP6. Given the significant variations in the input waste materials used for recyclate production, comparing their properties directly is neither valid nor scientifically appropriate.

LOOP 3 Cycle 1 pouches were mixed with household waste, sorted, and recycled; a process referred to as LOOP 3 Cycle 2 in the project. A comparison of properties such as OIT, MFR, and mechanical characteristics reveals differences in recyclate quality between the two cycles. The higher OIT observed in Cycle 2 may be attributed to the stabilizers used during the production of LOOP 3 Cycle 1 PE PCRs. The input material for LOOP 3 Cycle 2 consisted of 50% PE PCR from Cycle 1, and stabilizers were added again at the same concentration during the production of Cycle 2 PE PCR. Analytical detection would be helpful to determine the cause of the OIT increase.

The decrease in mechanical properties observed in Cycle 2 can be attributed to polymer degradation during multiple processing cycles or, more likely, to the higher proportion of inclusions (such as gels and bubbles) present in the films made from LOOP 3 Cycle 2 PE PCR.

Table 1: Overview - Resin properties of PE PCRs produced by different recycling cascades (all at pilot scale)

Recycling Cascades:			Recycling Cascade 1	Recycling Cascade 2	Recycling Cascade 2
Input Waste:			French household flexible post-consumer waste	B2B scenario: pouches of mono-material designed by CIRCULAR FoodPack (with high coffee leftovers inside)	TBS sorted pouches from the mixed household waste
PCR properties	Unit	Norm	LOOP 1	LOOP 2	LOOP 3
Density	[g/cm ³]	ISO 1183-1	0.931 ± 0.006	0.901 ± 0.007	0.921 ± 0.001 (cycle1) 0.909 ± 0.003 (cycle2)
MFR	[g/10 min]	ISO 1183-1	0.766	0.780	0.812 (cycle 1) 1.051 (cycle 2)
MVR	[cm ³ /10 min]	ISO 1183-1	0.950	0.985	
Melting Temperature	[°C]	ISO 11357-3	112 / 123	108 / 125	107 / 124 (cycle 1) 108 / 125 (cycle 2)
OIT	Min	ISO 11357-6	9.29	13.88	> 14 (cycle 1) > 38 (cycle 2)
VOC Level	mg/kg	Based on ASTM D4526	0.5 (for BPs < 100°C) 0.7 (for BPs < 200°C)	1.8 (for BPs < 100°C) 3.7 (for BPs < 200°C)	2.6 (for BPs < 100°C) 4.6 (for BPs < 200°C) (cycle 2)
Deinking efficiency ^(***)	%	-	Not measurable since initial level is unknown.	76% (Cu Removal) ^(*) 36% (Cu removal) ^(**)	90% (Cu removal) (cycle1) ^(*) >95% (Cu removal) (cycle2) ^(**)
Film properties	Unit	Norm			
Tensile modulus MD / TD	[MPa]	ISO 527-3	132 / 159 (cast film)	170 (MD, blown film)	127 / 147 (cycle 1, cast film) 258 (MD) (cycle 1, blown film) 131 / 154 (cycle 2, blown film)
Tensile strength MD / TD	[MPa]	ISO 527-3	25.6 / 18.9 (cast film)	26.9 / 17.3 (blown film)	34.9 / 29.6 (cycle 1, cast film) 27 (MD) (cycle 1, blown film) 17.3 / 15.7 (cycle 2, blown film)

Tensile elongation MD / TD	[%]	ISO 527-3	494 / 657 (cast film)	559 / 536 (blown film)	652 / 782 (cycle 1, cast film) 530 (MD) (cycle 1, blown film) 429 / 636 (cycle 2, blown film)
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(*) Measured at Fraunhofer IVV by ICP-MS (see Deliverable **D4.3**⁵ for detailed description of the methodology and results discussion.)

(**) Measured at UGENT by ICP-OES, methodology explained in section 3.2.1

(***) Deinking efficiency of recyclates as pellets

3.2. LOOP 2 and LOOP 3 PE PCRs by Recycling Cascade 2

3.2.1. LOOP 2: B2B scenario Mono-Material Pouches Designed by the Project Team, with High Coffee Residue

The deinking efficiencies of the deinked LOOP 2 materials (Material A and Material B) were analyzed at UGent for each processing step—after deinking and after the rinsing step—as shown in Figure 17. Since the deinked material batches were quite heterogeneous due to the large flake size, ball milling was applied to obtain homogeneous material for analysis. Following homogenization, the copper (Cu) content, which indicates the presence of blue colorant, was measured in triplicate using ICP-OES at UGent.

ICP-OES Analysis at UGent:

Optical emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma (ICP-OES) was performed using a Thermo Scientific iCAP 7200, equipped with Qtegra Software and a CETAC AXP 560 autosampler. Calibration standards (0.001–20 ppm) were prepared from a XVI Certipur multielement standard solution. For sample preparation, 0.2 g of plastic was digested via microwave digestion in 80 vol% HNO₃ (65%, Sigma-Aldrich). The samples were gradually heated to 200 °C over 40 minutes, followed by a 20-minute hold at 200 °C to ensure complete digestion. The digested solutions were then diluted to 25 mL with double-distilled water, filtered using a 0.45 µm syringe filter (PP filter media, CHROMAFIL), and analyzed by ICP-OES.

As the blue colorant responsible for staining the plastics contains copper (Cu), the deinking efficiency was assessed based on the reduction in Cu content after processing.

According to the results, the Cu content decreased by 36% in Material A and 27% in Material B following the deinking process (Table 1, see the column for LOOP 2). These relatively low deinking efficiencies are likely due to re-adsorption of the blue pigment onto the plastic film during the deinking process.

⁵ Deliverable D4.3: “Characterization of input material, benchmarking of cleaning processes” (Public), by Fraunhofer.

Figure 17: Deinked LOOP 2 materials at Hydrodyn: A) Material A with 10 mm flake size before deinking, after deinking at 80°C and after rinsing and drying; B) Material B with 20 mm flake size before deinking, after deinking at 75°C and after rinsing and drying.

3.2.2. LOOP 3: TBS sorted Food Packaging Pouches from Mixed Household Waste

LOOP 3 Cycle 1 Material (L3C1):

A 90% ink removal efficiency (based on copper reduction) was measured for the PE PCR of L3C1 food packaging pouches, produced via Recycling Cascade 2—which includes water-based deinking, mechanical recycling, and deodorization. The copper content was analyzed using ICP-MS at Fraunhofer IVV (see Table 1).

LOOP 3 Cycle 2 Material (L3C2):

Copper content in the three materials shown in Figure 12 was measured using ICP-OES, with triplicate measurements for each sample, following the same procedure described for LOOP 2 materials (see Section 3.2). After accounting for the copper contribution from L3C1 material—which was incorporated at a 50% ratio into L3C2—the cast film produced from L3C2 PE PCRs showed a 98% reduction in copper content relative to the original input material.

Unlike the L3C1 material, the water-based deinking of L3C2 was performed by a different subcontractor under distinct processing conditions, which included the use of developed scavengers. The detailed deinking procedures for each material are described in Section 2.4.

Although the upscaling trials for both LOOP 2 and L3C2 were conducted at the same subcontractor, the addition of scavengers to the optimized water-based medium led to a significant improvement in deinking efficiency, as illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Left: LOOP 2 recyclate deinked at Hydrodyn under optimized conditions. Right: LOOP 3 Cycle 2 recyclate deinked at Hydrodyn using the newly developed water-based medium.

3.3. LOOP 2 and LOOP 3 PE PCRs by Recycling Cascade 1

In addition to Recycling Cascade 2, Recycling Cascade 1 was also applied at small-technical scale for the recycling of materials from LOOP 2 and LOOP 3 (Cycle 1). The resulting PE PCRs are shown in Figure 19, while their properties are detailed in Table 2 and Table 3. These tables present comparative data from both Recycling Cascade 1 (small-technical scale) and Recycling Cascade 2 for the PE PCRs from LOOP 2 and LOOP 3.

Figure 19: Left: Recyclate from LOOP 2 material after dissolution-based recycling (Recycling Cascade 1). Right: Recyclate from LOOP 2 material after deinking and mechanical recycling (Recycling Cascade 2).

The physical and mechanical properties of the recyclates do not differ significantly between the two cascades. However, a notable difference in color is clearly visible, particularly in the recyclates from LOOP 3, Cycle 1, with Cascade 2 producing material with higher haze, as confirmed by haze measurements.

To assess deinking efficiency, ICP-MS measurements were conducted at Fraunhofer, and the results are presented in Table 3. The reductions in copper (Cu) and titanium (Ti) contents were measured, as Cu is a main component of blue ink and Ti of white ink. Despite the more pronounced visual reduction of blue ink observed, only a slightly higher Cu reduction of 91%

was achieved using Cascade 1, compared to 90% with Cascade 2. However, Cascade 1 resulted in a significantly higher Ti reduction of 98%, whereas Cascade 2 showed strongly scattered Ti values, making it difficult to determine a clear reduction.

Table 2: Overview of Resin Properties of PE PCR from LOOP 2 via Two Recycling Cascades

Recycling Cascade:			Recycling Cascade 1	Recycling Cascade 2
Input Waste:			B2B scenario: pouches of mono-material designed (with high coffee leftovers inside)	
PCR properties	Unit	Norm	LOOP 2 (technical scale)	LOOP 2 (D6.3 ⁶)
MFR	[g/10 min]	ISO 1183-1	0.773	0.780
MVR	[cm ³ /10 min]	ISO 1183-1	0.999	0.985
Melting Temperature	[°C]	ISO 11357-3	108 / 125	108 / 125
OIT	Min	ISO 11357-6	12.72	13.88
Film properties			Recycling Cascade 1	Recycling Cascade 2
Tensile modulus MD / TD	[MPa]	ISO 527-3	126 / 153 (cast film)	170 (MD, blown film)
Tensile strength MD / TD	[MPa]	ISO 527-3	26.4 / 21.3 (cast film)	26.9 / 17.3 (blown film)
Tensile elongation MD / TD	[%]	ISO 527-3	507 / 671 (cast film)	559 / 536 (blown film)

Table 3: Overview of Resin properties of PE PCR from LOOP 3 by Two recycling cascades

Recycling Cascade:			Recycling Cascade 1	Recycling Cascade 2
Input Waste:			TBS sorted pouches from the mixed household waste	
PCR properties	Unit	Norm	LOOP 3 (technical scale)	LOOP 3 (D6.4 ⁷)
Density	[g/cm ³]	ISO 1183-1	0.921 (cycle 1)	0.914
MFR	[g/10 min]	ISO 1183-1	0.950 (cycle 1)	0.812 (cycle 1)
Melting Temperature	[°C]	ISO 11357-3	107 / 124 (cycle 1)	107 / 124 (cycle 1)
Deinking efficiency (***) (Ti, Cu)	%	internal procedure	91% (Cu) (cycle 1) ^(*) 98% (Ti) (cycle 1) ^(*)	90% (Cu) (cycle 1) ^(*) 42% (Ti) (cycle 1) ^(*)
Film properties			Recycling Cascade 1	Recycling Cascade 2
Tensile modulus MD / TD	[MPa]	ISO 527-3	129 / 150 (cycle 1, cast film)	127 / 147 (cycle 1, cast film)

⁶ Deliverable D6.3: "Demonstration of circular use in flexible food packaging based on B2B collection" (Confidential), by NESTLE.

⁷ Deliverable D6.4: "Demonstration of circular use in flex. food packaging based on CFP technologies" (Public), by POLY.

Tensile strength MD / TD	[MPa]	ISO 527-3	32 / 26 (cycle 1, cast film)	34.9 / 29.6 (cycle 1, cast film)
Tensile elongation MD / TD	[%]	ISO 527-3	616 / 777 (cycle 1, cast film)	652 / 782 (cycle 1, cast film)
Dart drop impact	[g/μm]		2.78 (cycle 1, cast film)	3.62 (cycle 1, cast film)
Haze	[%]		11.7 (cycle 1, cast film)	15.3 (cycle 1, cast film)

(*) Measured at Fraunhofer IVV by ICP-MS (see Deliverable **D4.3**⁸ for detailed description of the methodology and results discussion.)

(**) Measured at UGENT by ICP-OES

(***) Deinking efficiency of recyclates as pellets

3.4. Tracer removal efficiencies for LOOP 3

An important outcome of WP3 was the effective removal of the tracers used in LOOP 3 materials for food packaging sorting. The selected tracer types and their concentrations in inks are detailed in the public Deliverables 3.8⁹ and 5.5¹⁰. Efficient removal of these tracers is critical when the resulting PCRs are intended for use in new flexible packaging products. Table 4 illustrates the reduction of Y and Yb markers, with both Recycling Cascades 1 and 2 achieving removal efficiencies exceeding 95%, demonstrating their effective deinking capabilities.

Table 4: Reduction efficiency for the tracer elements, Y and Yb after recycling

(With respect to reference flakes before deinking) (*)		Y [%]	Yb [%]
Measurements by Fraunhofer (WP4) (***)	Recycling Cascade 1 (**)	99.2	99.3
	Recycling Cascade 2 (**)	91.3	92.2

(*) Shredded laminate flakes

(**) Recyclates as pellets

(***) Measured at Fraunhofer IVV by ICP-MS (see Deliverable **D4.3**⁸ for detailed description of the methodology and results discussion.)

⁸ Deliverable D4.3: "Characterization of input material, benchmarking of cleaning processes" (Public), by Fraunhofer.

⁹ Deliverable D3.8: "Guidelines on Design for Recycling" (Public), by UM.

¹⁰ Deliverable D5.5: "Guidelines for tracer printing in packaging for effective sorting, management after use" (Public), by SIEGWERK.

4. COST ANALYSIS OF THE TWO RECYCLING CASCADES

The cost analysis of two different recycling cascades (based respectively on dissolution-based recycling and water-based deinking and delamination) has been evaluated using the Net Present Value (NPV) and the Internal Rate of Return (IRR). The analysis of the investment cost includes an evaluation of both the purchase cost of the equipment (capital expenditure, CAPEX) and the operating cost (operating expense, OPEX). CAPEX is subject to depreciation, while OPEX is not depreciable. **Fixed capital investment** includes the total cost of designing, manufacturing, purchasing and installing a unit, as well as the modifications required to install the unit. Design costs include detailed design of equipment, control systems, engineering costs, supervision, etc. **The operating costs** of the investment include direct production costs (maintenance and repair costs, consumption of raw materials, electricity, water, natural gas, licenses and patents, etc.), fixed costs (taxes, property insurance, interest, employee overheads, rents, etc.), and general costs (administrative expenses, sales, marketing and research and development activities). Also, **other costs** are included, such as administrative charges (inspection, project management, engineering operating costs, etc.).

The viability of the investment is determined by cash flows and discount rates and was based on the calculation of the Net Present Value (NPV) and the internal rate of return (IRR). The Net Present Value (NPV) refers to the net benefit in terms of present value for all the years of the investment studied, in relation to the cost of funds used for the investment. A positive NPV value indicates that the investment is profitable. The greater the NPV, the more efficient the investment considered is. The internal rate of return; IRR refers to the return on investment when the present value of future cash flows equals the initial cost of the investment. The higher the IRR, the more desirable an investment is. NTUA has built an automated tool for the calculation of NPV and IRR based on the common equations and models.

Regarding CIRCULAR FoodPack's innovations, cost assessment and estimation of NPV and IRR have been conducted by NTUA, for two different recycling cascades, one including the water-based purification method (Recycling Cascade 2) and the other the dissolution-based (Recycling Cascade 1). Data used were extracted from Deliverable D7.4¹¹, Deliverable D8.4¹² and literature search. Input flows and cost of utilities of each process included in the 2 different recycling cascades are presented in the following tables.

Table 5: Input flows of the 2 different recycling cascades (based on D7.4¹¹). Note: Recycling Cascade 1 is suitable for all investigated feedstocks. Recycling Cascade 2 is applicable to mono-material based laminates.

	Recycling Cascade 1				Recycling Cascade 2			
Pre-treatment	Oversorting	PE-rich mix flexibles: Food and non-food	1	t	Oversorting	PE-rich flexibles: Food	1	t
		Electricity	50	kWh		Electricity	50	kWh
		Compressed air	200	m ³ /h		Compressed air	200	m ³ /h

¹¹ Deliverable D7.4: "Defined scenarios and data inventories for final sustainability assessment" (Public), by UGENT.

¹² Deliverable D8.4: "Feasibility parameters and investment analysis" (Confidential), by NTUA.

	Shredding	PE-rich flexibles	0.94	t	Shredding	PE-rich flexibles/Food	0.98	t	
		Electricity	169	kWh		Electricity	176	kWh	
	Washing	PE-rich flakes	0.94	t	Washing	PE-rich flakes	0.98	t	
		Electricity	35.156	kWh		Electricity	36.652	kWh	
		Water	391.5	kg		Water	408.2	kg	
	Grinding	PE-rich flakes	0.94	t	Grinding	PE-rich flakes	0.98	t	
		Electricity	66	kWh		Electricity	69	kWh	
	Float-sink separation	PE-rich flakes	0.94	t	Float-sink separation	PE-rich flakes	0.98	t	
		Electricity	18.8	kWh		Electricity	19.6	kWh	
		Water	391.5	kg		Water	408.2	kg	
	Purification / recycling	Continuous dissolving Recovered	PE-rich flakes	1.11	kg	Delamination	Confidential		
			Recovered solvent	Confidential	kg	Deinking	Confidential		
Electricity			0.45	kWh	Preconditioning	Pre-treated PE flakes	1	t	
Heat			2.38	MJ		Electricity	17	kWh	
Virgin solvent			0.01	kg	Melting	PE flakes	1	t	
Multistage filtration		PE solution (incl. residues)	13.32	kg		Electricity	550	kWh	
		Electricity	0.18	kWh	Filtration	PE flakes	1	t	
		Heat	0.32	MJ		Electricity	26	kWh	
Residual treatment and PE purification		Electricity	0.55	kWh	Final degassing	PE flakes	0.95	t	
		Heat	2.85	MJ		Electricity	5	kWh	
Multiple stage drying		PE solution and removed PE solution from residue	13.21	kg	Homogenisation	PE flakes	0.95	t	
		Electricity	1.25	kWh		Electricity	15	kWh	
		Heat	2.38	MJ	Pelletizing	PE flakes	0.95	t	
Regranulation		PE melt	1	kg		Electricity	26	kWh	
		Electricity	0.05	kWh					
Auxiliary for all the processes		Nitrogen	0.05	kg					
Post treatment		Infrared treatment	PE PCR pellets	1	t	Infrared treatment	PE PCR pellets	1	t
	Air for cooling		confidential		Air for cooling		confidential		
	Electricity		60	kWh	Electricity		60	kWh	
	Thermal treatment	PE PCR pellets	1	t	Thermal treatment	PE PCR pellets	1	t	
		Air	confidential			Air	confidential		
		Electricity	25	kWh		Electricity	25	kWh	

Table 6: Cost of the utilities of the 2 different recycling cascades. Note: Recycling Cascade 1 is suitable for all investigated feedstocks. Recycling Cascade 2 is applicable to mono-material based laminates.

Freshwater	1 €/m ³	Deliverable 7.4 ¹³
Electricity	0.124 €/kWh	EU average (Eurostat data)
Heat	0.060 €/kWh	EU average (Eurostat data)

¹³ Deliverable D7.4: "Defined scenarios and data inventories for final sustainability assessment" (Public), by UGENT.

The cost of some of the raw materials and additives used in the processes is considered confidential and the total raw materials costs are not presented. In addition, personnel costs are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Personnel costs for the production of PE PCR (shown in D 7.4¹⁴)

Pre-treatment	50,000/person per year	1.5 person / kt per year
Dissolution-based purification and recycling (Creasolv®)	800,400	€/y; Overall staff working in 4 shifts
Water-based purification (delamination, deinking)	50,000/person per year	1.5 person / kt per year
Recompounding: densification, melting, pelletizing	50,000/person per year	1.5 person / kt per year
Deodorization	50,000/person per year	1.5 person / kt per year

The analysis of CAPEX and other costs of the 2 cascades are given in the following table.

Table 8: Analysis of CAPEX and Operating Costs for the Two Recycling Cascades. Note: Recycling Cascade 1 is suitable for all investigated feedstocks, while Recycling Cascade 2 is applicable only to mono-material-based laminates.

		Recycling Cascade 1	Recycling Cascade 2
CAPEX (€)	Pre-treatment	4,727,000	4,727,000
	Purification and recycling	7,063,567	6,664,536
	Deodorization	704,000	704,000
Other costs (€/y)	Pre-treatment	134,762	134,762
	Purification and recycling	855,301	366,459
	Deodorization	46,146	46,146

The flow charts of the two different developed cascades have already been presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

The production size of the recycling plant depends on the quantity of waste that will be treated per year. In CIRCULAR FoodPack calculations, the annual amount of treated plastic waste is considered around 6,400 t. The total capital cost of the equipment required for the operation of the two recycling cascades is given in Table 9. The investment cost includes also an initial working capital, which is estimated at € 500,000, while the investment is expected to operate for 15 years. The initial working capital is necessary to allow the company to cover initial operating costs until it gains the first revenues from the sale of the recycled PE. The operating costs of the investment include the cost of raw materials, the consumption of energy and water required for the operation of the unit, the cost of employing staff, but also other operating costs, such as insurance and maintenance costs, as well as administrative expenses. The total operating cost for each cascade, for the first year of operation, is presented in Table 9. In the calculation of the operating expenses for the 15 years of operation of the investment, an increase of 2% per year has been calculated due to the inflationary increase. Other costs required for the operating of the units, given in the table for the first year of operation, include indirect costs, such as construction expenses to keep the equipment running, legal expenses, contractors' fee and contingency, as well as manufacturing costs and general expenses. These costs are also subject to a 2% inflationary increase. The investment is made exclusively using

¹⁴ Deliverable D7.4: "Defined scenarios and data inventories for final sustainability assessment" (Public), by UGENT.

equity capital, while the depreciation method that is followed is the annual constant depreciation method.

Table 9: Cost analysis of the 2 different recycling cascades. Note: Recycling Cascade 1 is suitable for all investigated feedstocks. Recycling Cascade 2 is applicable to mono-material based laminates.

	Recycling Cascade 1	Recycling Cascade 2
CAPEX (€)	12,994,567	12,595,536
OPEX (€)	5,468,638	4,691,102
Other costs (€)	1,036,209	558,314
PE price (€/kg)	1.40	1.25
NPV (€)	2,580,140	2,677,796
IRR (%)	15.19	15.42

As can be seen, both cases require similar capital investment (CAPEX). CreaSolv® technology in LOOP 1 is more expensive (7,063,500 €) than water-based purification technology (4,233,390 €), however, also the water-based purification technology includes the recompounding step (densification, melting and pelletizing) which raises the final price of the capital investment.

In addition to the investment cost, Table 9 includes the Net Present Value (NPV) and the internal rate of return (IRR), as well as the price for the recycled PE that represents a feasible project that could enter the market and be profitable (NPV>0, IRR>15%). The price of the recycled PE is estimated at 1.40 €/kg for the solvent-based process and 1.25 €/kg for the mechanical recycling with water-based delamination/deinking process. These prices are in line with the current market price for virgin PE, which ranges from 0.80 €/kg to 1.85 €/kg. Both cases yield positive Net Present Values (NPVs) and Internal Rates of Return (IRRs). The recycled product's price alignment with market rates suggests that both processes have the potential to create a viable business opportunity, suitable for both food and non-food packaging applications.

Figure 20 presents the breakdown of CAPEX, OPEX and other costs to the various processes used for the recycling of plastic waste, both for the water and solvent-based cascades. In both recycling cases, the purification process represents the highest cost component in both CAPEX and OPEX, followed by the pre-treatment stage. By improving efficiency in purification and pre-treatment steps and integrating renewable energy sources, it may be possible to reduce overall costs further. This would improve the business case and enhance the competitiveness of the recycled PE.

Figure 20: Cost analysis for the two recycling cascades a) Recycling Cascade 1 includes dissolution-based purification, b) Recycling Cascade 2 includes water-based deinking/delamination.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Since the beginning of the project, a range of sorting, pretreatment, and recycling processes were assessed to ensure compliance with the quality standards required for food packaging. The primary objective was to achieve these standards while minimizing the cost difference between recycled material and virgin material. To this end, UGENT and Fraunhofer analyzed the results of Tasks 3.2 to 3.5, utilizing the database (refer to Deliverables D3.1¹⁵) to identify process chains capable of achieving the desired quality. These processes include water washing and water-based deinking as pretreatment steps, and/or dissolution-based recycling for purification and recycling. Mass and energy balances for these process chains were calculated, covering yields, water consumption, solvent usage, and energy requirements for solvent recovery. Basic cost estimates were also developed to support sustainability assessments in WP7 and WP8.

For the input streams provided by WP2 (household flexible packaging waste) and WP6 (B2B-collected packaging and packaging with tracers for closed-loop recycling) intended for WP6 demonstrator loops, optimized process chains (called as recycling cascade here) were developed based on the purification requirements and cost structures. The design of these process chains prioritized achieving high-quality PE PCRs by focusing on maximum purification efficiency while maintaining cost-effectiveness.

A critical factor in determining the most suitable recycling cascade was the composition and characteristics of the input flexible packaging waste. Insights gained from WP3 indicated that Recycling Cascade 2 (which includes water-based delamination/deinking, and mechanical recycling) was unsuitable for processing French household flexible post-consumer waste. This limitation arose from the heterogeneous nature of the packaging materials, which are not tailored for delamination and thus significantly hinder the effectiveness of water-based delamination and deinking processes. The mixed material composition led to suboptimal separation and removal of inks, highlighting the need for alternative or enhanced recycling strategies to handle such complex waste streams efficiently. Dissolution-based recycling (Recycling Cascade 1) provided very effective purification for this type of waste and enabled the production of machine direction oriented (MDOPE) and sealing films at PE PCR concentrations of 50 and 100%, respectively.

On the other hand, the PE based mono-material flexible packaging laminates tailored with a debondable/delamination primer tested by the partners in the project have been effectively deinked by means of water-based delamination and deinking processes (Recycling Cascade 2). One advantage of these processes is that there is available infrastructure in Europe that can adapt the required process parameters at scale, such as the subcontractors used in CIRCULAR FoodPack project, Hydrodyn, NTCP, being the reason for the selection for this Recycling Cascade 2 for these input wastes. Deinking efficiency over 95% has been reached in water-based deinking after the integration of special scavengers developed in the project for the elimination of the color staining on the PE PCRs, which has been one of the highlights of the project. This cascade is considered the best choice for targeted streams such as diverted streams or B2B streams which have a dedicated collection infrastructure.

¹⁵ Deliverable D3.1: "Database of studied waste fractions, their analytical results and process cascades they were subjected to" (Public), by Fraunhofer.

Another key advancement in the project was the incorporation of deodorization technology into both recycling cascades. The in-depth understanding of plastic deodorization, combined with the application of infrared-based deodorization technology, enabled the achievement of over 98% deodorization efficiency across a variety of plastic waste streams enabling a safe operation environment to produce the films.

Regarding costs, both prices of PE PCR producing without considering the sorting step are in line with the current market price for virgin PE (0.80 - 1.85 €/kg). In both recycling cascades, the purification processes represent the highest cost component in both CAPEX and OPEX. Regarding water-based purification, the price for the recycled PE should be higher than 1.25 €/kg to achieve a viable integration into the market. On the other hand, although dissolution-based recycling is more expensive than water-based purification technology, also the Recycling Cascade 2 includes the recompounding step, which increases the final price of CAPEX. The price of the recycled PE is estimated at 1.40 €/kg for Recycling Cascade 1 and 1.25 €/kg for Recycling Cascade 2. The process feasibility could be improved by improving efficiency in purification and pre-treatment steps and integrating renewable energy sources.

